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Putting brakes on Expedition Cruise Tourism in Svalbard: exercising power at the expense of legitimacy?

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ABSTRACT

Ecosystems in the Arctic are affected by multiple stressors caused by climate and environmental changes, increased pollution and human activities. The changes are unprecedented, with considerable scientific uncertainties over their potential consequences. In such a situation the use of the precautionary principle can be justified in environmental management. The principle is still contested, and its implementation needs careful considerations to be experienced as legitimate. This article will use the new regulatory amendments in Svalbard as a case to examine what preconditions must be in place to maintain legitimacy in environmental policy making when the precautionary principle is being applied. Based on a compilation of ship positional data, we assess the spatio-temporal distribution of cruise ships in Svalbard from 2011 to 2022 and the potential impacts on selected species. We then discuss the legitimacy of the regulatory amendments and the application of the precautionary principle. Our results show significant growth in the amount, distribution, and mileage of expedition cruise vessels' length of travel. While a precautionary approach to management is wise in a situation in which more stressors than ever are threatening Arctic wildlife, a more transparent and inclusive regulatory process would have strengthened the legitimacy of regulations and reduced conflict.

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Introduction

Due to climate change, the Arctic biophysical system is trending away from its former state and into a period of unprecedented change (Box et al., 2019). The changes have been described as rapid and cascading (Dannevig et al., 2023), with impacts that are difficult to predict (Vincent, 2020). Parallel to this development, tourism has become a major factor influencing changes in the coupled socio-ecological systems of the Arctic (Schlegel et al., 2023). While it may offer economic opportunities to local communities, it also causes social stress and affects wildlife and fragile ecosystems (Chen et al., 2021).

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The stress caused by the growing expedition cruise tourism is of particular concern in this article (Hansen-Magnusson & Gehrke, 2023; Ren et al., 2021). Expeditions cruise tourism consists of ships operating with a passenger capacity of 13–500 passengers but also includes smaller vessels with a capacity of 12 or less (Ministry of Justice and Public Security, NOU:2022:1). The format of this type of cruise tourism is more flexible, with less rigid travel itineraries and with minimal reliance on infrastructure, allowing for an ‘explorer format’ as described by the Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (AECO). Wildlife figure heavily into expedition cruise tourism in the Arctic, and allows tourists to ‘explore untouched wilderness’ on foot or by zodiac or kayak. Expedition cruise tourism operators often rely on charismatic species, such as polar bears, arctic foxes, reindeer and walruses, in their marketing. Other, more specific activities such as ‘ski and sail’ – where the goal is ski touring – are also popular. However, ‘Ski and sail’ make use of much smaller vessels, have fewer passengers, and go ashore in different places than bigger cruise vessels (MOSJ).

The expedition cruises are marketed as more exclusive wilderness experiences as their passengers can go ashore at multiple sites along the shore and thereby get closer to the Arctic nature and wildlife. Lahr et al. (2019, p. 31) mapped and showed a correspondence between tourists’ landing sites and the actual presence of seabird colonies, occurrence of polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) and walrus (*Odobenus rosmarus*) haul out sites in Svalbard. Studies from other parts of the world suggest that increased ship traffic can have a negative impact on wildlife, particularly seabirds (Merkel et al., 2023) and marine mammals (Bejder et al., 2022).

This indicates a potential disturbance at tourists’ visiting sites that host vulnerable species. Tourists may disturb wildlife at the landing site (i.e. on-land disturbance at the colonies or haul-out sites) as well as at sea (e.g. underwater noise disturbance from marine vessels) (Halliday et al., 2020; Llobet et al., 2023); moreover, the vessels might disturb the birds’ foraging activities (Merkel et al., 2023; Velando & Munilla, 2011).

Assessing the effects of human disturbance on wildlife is still a major challenge. First, wildlife responses to human disturbance can vary among species and span multiple levels, from immediate behavioral effects to long-term physiological and demographic impacts (Madsen et al., 2009). With uncertainties at each step, the move from disturbance effects at individual level to impact at population level has been described as a ‘fundamental ecological problem’ (Pirotta et al., 2018)

Second, as indicated by Hagen et al. (2012), disturbance effects are determined by not only the number of visitors but also the type of disturbance, timing, seasonality, and characteristics of the specific geographical site. Knowledge from one site is not necessarily transferable to another.

Finally, the cumulative effects of stressors need to be considered. Multiple sources of disturbance are likely to occur in an area at any given time, together with other, concurrent environmental and ecological processes (Pirotta et al., 2018). This makes it difficult to attribute causation to any one disturbance or stressor. This challenge is reinforced by the rapid and unprecedented environmental changes in the Arctic caused by climate change.

The above literature indicates the challenges of obtaining scientific certainty about the effects of increasing tourism traffic in Svalbard. From an environmental management perspective, the precautionary principle could be applied in this situation. The precautionary principle implies that when there are considerable scientific uncertainties over potential harm, policies should be cautious and err on the side of the environment

(Kriebel et al., 2001). The principle should be used when there are considerable scientific uncertainties over ‘causality, magnitude, probability and nature of harm’ (UNESCO/COMEST, 2005).

According to Kriebel et al. (2001) the precautionary principle has its roots in German environmental policy under the name *Vorsorgeprinzip* and has developed in the last decades to become one of the guiding principles in the European Union’s environmental laws. The principle is now widely used in environmental issues where there are uncertainties about the long-term effects of today’s practices such as in international fisheries (Lauck et al., 2020), climate change (Farber, 2015) and biodiversity (Cooney, 2004). In Norway, national park management has traditionally been based on the precautionary principle, (Higham et al., 2016)

There should, however, always be some scientific evidence to support the application of the precautionary principle in order to avoid misuse and speculation, and the precautionary principle should be replaced by other principles when it is possible to quantify probabilities and outcomes (UNESCO/COMEST, 2005). When new scientific evidence emerges about the levels of human impact that actually cause harm, the regulations can be adjusted accordingly (DeFur & Kaszuba, 2002). The precautionary principle should also be accompanied by governance mechanisms adapted to the particular socio-ecological ambiguities at stake (DeFur & Kaszuba, 2002).

With the rapid and multiple changes facing the Arctic, one may expect an increasing use of the precautionary principle. The principle is still contested, and its implementation needs careful considerations to be experienced as legitimate. In this article we will use the new regulatory amendments in Svalbard as a case to examine challenges linked to legitimacy in policy making when the precautionary principle is being applied. Legitimacy is important for governance to be efficient and have support in the long run.

To achieve this we will (a) examine the sparse research on disturbance effects on wildlife in Svalbard and (b) calculate the distances traveled by expedition cruise ships in Svalbard from 2011 to 2019 to obtain a precise measure of changes in expedition cruise traffic, and based on the above, (c) employ qualitative material from the hearing process in Svalbard to discuss the legitimacy of the new regulations based on the precautionary principle.

Our main research question is: *What preconditions needs to be in place for environmental regulations based on the precautionary principle to be considered legitimate by stakeholders?*

Legitimacy in environmental decision-making

In legitimate policy initiatives, stakeholders should perceive the substance of the policy as reasonable and the process of policy development as appropriate. When regulations are based on the precautionary principle, there is less scientific evidence to back up the policies. This may challenge the legitimacy of regulatory changes. The amendment process in Longyearbyen has in previous literature been described as eroding public trust in governance structures in Svalbard (Kaltenborn et al., 2024). In what follows, we examine the legitimacy concept to better understand why the process was perceived as eroding public trust, and what preconditions are needed to build legitimacy.

The literature on legitimacy often differentiates between legal and political legitimacy. Legal legitimacy refers to law in that a new proposal complies with current laws and regulations and, therefore, can be regarded as valid or fair. Political legitimacy, in contrast, has been defined as ‘the acceptance and justification of a shared rule by a community’

(Bernstein, 2011, p. 20), and it is this type of legitimacy we refer to in the following. Political legitimacy can be understood as a normative concept, resting on the principles of justness and appropriateness (Wallner, 2008, p. 423).

A fruitful starting point for discussing legitimacy in environmental regulations is the distinction between input- and output-oriented accounts of legitimacy proposed by Scharpf (1999). Input-oriented accounts of legitimacy indicate the procedures ahead of regulations and whether the people affected by these regulations have been informed and participated in the political process. In more recent literature this source of legitimacy is called procedural legitimacy, as it refers to procedures and process (Dellmuth et al., 2019).

Participation in such processes, when understood as inclusion, can be defined as the 'inclusion of nonstate actors, such as members of the public or as organized stakeholders, in any stage of governmental policy making including implementation' (Wesselink et al., 2011, p. 2688). In this respect, procedural legitimacy is directly linked to 'the fairness, inclusiveness, and quality of participation' (Birnbaum, 2016, p. 310). Ideally, all affected parties should be included and have a voice throughout the process.

While the level of involvement will vary, public participation is widely accepted as a fundamental part of contemporary environmental decision-making (Chilvers & Kearnes, 2020; Day, 1997). Public participation is often understood as legitimating regulatory processes and generating buy-in for potentially contentious decisions, and there are now a vast variety of efforts aimed at engaging citizens in resource management (Kurniawan et al., 2022).

Participatory mechanisms are often criticized, and participation to democratize environmental decision-making has been debated among scholars (Chilvers & Kearnes, 2020; Marquardt & Lederer, 2022; Swyngedouw, 2022). In addition to being seen as a public relations exercise and a form of corporate greenwashing (Almeida et al., 2023), participation is often experienced as both frustrating and disempowering by the citizens navigating participatory processes (Johnson et al., 2021; Sveinsdóttir & Johnson, 2023). This, in turn, may erode trust in decision-making processes and negatively impact democratic legitimacy.

Paavola (2004, p. 65) argued that the legitimacy of environmental regulations depends on both distribution of power in decision-making and procedures that include recognition, hearing, and participation. These principles have been well-established in environmental processes in Norway since the introduction of the Nature Diversity Act in 2009 (Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2009). While participation is now an explicit goal, the level of democratic decision-making can still be questioned. Birnbaum (2016, p. 318) warned that 'more' co-governance is not always better for the overall legitimacy of regulations, as in many contexts, powerful, vested interests are not balanced well with the views of the broader public.

Output-oriented accounts of legitimacy encompass the *performance* of the governance structure, whether the problem-solving is efficient and serves the common good (Birnbaum, 2016, p. 310). Legitimacy is thus based on an assessment of the intended results and whether the government structure has achieved its aims. At the local level, performance (output) legitimacy is related to the experience of local benefits or some form of compensation if stakeholders experience a loss as well as a lack of negative impacts (Paavola, 2004; Prno & Scott Slocombe, 2012).

Birnbaum (2016) argued that the performance of a given structure/policy can be interpreted in two ways: first, the output (i.e. content and quality) of the decision or forms of

management. In the case of the amended regulations in Svalbard, this would mean performance interpreted in terms of the quality of the content (e.g. the scientific basis for the regulatory changes). This is achieved when a policy aligns, to a certain degree, with stakeholders and the public (Wallner, 2008). For this to happen, the content of the policies must be convincing, and trust must be built. Hagen et al. (2012, p. 10) have previously criticized the scientific grounds of environmental management in Svalbard. They called for a shift toward more integrated and evidence-based management that will contribute to ‘more trusted and reliable, and thereby acceptable, decisions in the management of growing tourism activity in Svalbard’.

The second interpretation of performance concerns the wider social or environmental effects of the policy; the efficiency of regulations in terms of whether they can meet the stated objectives. In environmental regulations, these aims are often long term, and in Svalbard they concern the regulations’ ability to maintain Svalbard as ‘one of the best managed wilderness areas in the world’ (Ministry of Justice and the Public Security, 2008-2009, p. 9).

Thus, the legitimacy of environmental regulations depends on both procedural and performance aspects. This is further challenged in a situation where the precautionary principle has been applied due to considerable scientific uncertainty. While Norwegian environmental planning aims to be knowledge-based (Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2012), more knowledge does not necessarily resolve conflicts of interest (Bay-Larsen, 2014). Different interpretations of available knowledge can lead to a questioning of the legitimacy of environmental processes (Dannevig & Dale, 2018). Lister (2003, p. 179) also remind us that legitimacy is context dependent, and will always be shaped by the approaches, perceptions and interests of the stakeholders.

In the analysis of our qualitative material we will examine the preconditions that need to be in place for environmental regulations based on the precautionary principle to be considered legitimate by stakeholders. We will examine how the affected actors (a) understand the process that leads to the regulations (input aspects) and how they (b) understand the content of the regulations, as well as the knowledge base anchoring the decisions, and whether the amended regulations are understood as being in line with, and contributing to, the aims of the environmental policies of Svalbard (output aspects). As the updated SEPA regulations (to be implemented in early 2025) have not yet been enacted, this analysis does not investigate the actual performance of the changes or the level of compliance.

New environmental regulation in svalbard

Svalbard, a high Arctic Archipelago (see [Figure 1](#)), is one of the world’s northernmost tourism destinations. Tourism development is encouraged by the Norwegian national policy in Svalbard (Ministry of Justice and Public Security, 2016, 2024), and the growth in tourism has been driven both by demand and been facilitated by sea ice reduction (Stocker et al., 2020), which is expanding the expedition cruise season (Dannevig et al., 2023; Schlegel et al., 2023).

The marine-based tourism in Svalbard has increased rapidly over the last few years (Olsen et al., 2020). Excluding the 2020 and 2021 seasons, which were strongly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a steady increase particularly in expedition cruise tourism [Environmental Monitoring of Svalbard and Jan Mayen (MOSJ), 2024]. According to MOSJ, the number of landing sites for the expedition cruise ships along

Regulation of access on Svalbard

- ! Access ban cultural heritage (1,6,/)
- ! Requirement for access guidelines for tour operators (1)
- Nature preserve - seasonal access ban
- Whole year access ban
- Seasonal access ban (1,2,3)
- Sone A - declaration of travel mandatory
- National Park (1,8,9,10,11)
- Nature preserve (1,2,3,4,5)
- Geotop preserve

Current laws and regulation

- 1) Forskrift om nasjonalparkene og naturreservatene på Svalbard
- 2) Forskrift om fredning av Bjørnøya naturreservat
- 3) Forskrift om fredning av Moffen naturreservat
- 4) Forskrift om fredning av Hopen naturreservat
- 5) Forskrift om Ossian Sars naturreservat
- 6) Forskrift om fredning av Virgohamna
- 7) Forskrift om ferdselsforbud ved Midterhukken
- 8) Forskrift om Sassen-Bunsow Land nasjonalpark
- 9) Forskrift om Van Mijenfjorden nasjonalpark
- 10) Forskrift om Indre Wijdefjorden nasjonalpark
- 11) Forskrift om Nordre Isfjorden nasjonalpark
- 12) Forskrift om Festningen geotopvernområde

Figure 1. Map of Svalbard with protected areas and sites.

Source: Norwegian Polar Institute.

the shore of the archipelago has increased from 140 in 2009 to 233 in 2022, and more boats are now sailing to the remote eastern part of Svalbard.

Svalbard is governed by Norway through the Svalbard Act of 1920 [implemented in 1925], and its environment is regulated by Norwegian authorities through the Svalbard Environmental Protection Act (SEPA, 2002/2012/2025). The SEPA states that Svalbard should be one of the world's best managed wilderness areas. In the case of conflict, environmental protection is prioritized over other economic or societal interests. As such, a strict application of the precautionary principle is emphasized, and in many respects, environmental legislation on Svalbard is stricter than the comparable legislation on mainland Norway (Kaltenborn et al., 2020, 2024). Policies and governance decisions in Svalbard are largely made at the government level, and practical management is carried out by the governor's staff based in Longyearbyen. Therefore, there is little room for influencing policies and decision-making by local interests (Kaltenborn et al., 2024).

Climate and environmental changes – combined with the expansion of tourism, including expedition cruises – have recently led to revised and stricter tourism regulations in the protected areas (covering 67% of the land masses) of Svalbard [Norwegian Environmental Agency (NEA), 2022]. The revised SEPA was implemented on January 1, 2025. The background for the regulatory changes is 'that it is necessary to protect the wilderness and the cultural heritage values in Svalbard from the increasing overall load from both tourism and climate change' (NEA, 2022, p. 5). The amendments include a ban on landings, except for 43 predesignated sites, and a cap of 200 passengers per ship. With reference to the long-term conservation objectives to keep the wilderness areas undisturbed, the precautionary principle was used extensively in the cover letter when the amendments were submitted to public hearings (NEA, 2022). The process surrounding the amendments caused fierce opposition in Longyearbyen (Kaltenborn et al., 2024), and the magnitude of the response illustrated the complexities of balancing long-term environmental interests with local user interests.

Arctic fauna and wilderness are the main attractions of Svalbard, and localities rich in wildlife naturally attract tourists (Lahr et al., 2019). Nevertheless, there is scant knowledge about the actual impact of tourist disturbance on the archipelago's wildlife.

Table 1. Studies specifically from Svalbard relevant to the disturbance effects of expedition cruise tourism.

Species	Type of disturbance	Disturbance consequences	Reference
Walrus	Tourists visit haul-out sites on land or by boat. Monitored by cameras	The walrus react very little to human visitations, but tourist-associated disturbances should be avoided to minimize the risk of cumulative impacts	Øren et al. (2018)
Reindeer	Humans on foot and hunting	Svalbard reindeer has become habituated to humans, and hunting has only a weak effect on them	Colman et al. (2001)
Polar bears	Snow mobile	Disturbed bears would run for 1–5 km. Some bears leave the ringed seal breathing hole if disturbed. Females with cubs are subjected to the strongest disturbance. Increased energy consumption but unknown long-term effects	Andersen and Aars (2008)
Arctic terns	Compared disturbance effects between terns in town and terns not used to human disturbance	Terns not used to humans return to their nest about 5 min after the disturbance, while terns in town return within a few tens of seconds. No difference in hatching success. More frequent disturbance can still threaten incubation and the whole population of terns	Syrova et al. (2019)

A few studies specifically from Svalbard relevant to the disturbance effects of expedition cruise tourism are listed in the [Table 1](#) below.

While we above describe the general challenges of measuring disturbance effects, these effects should also be considered in relation to the status of the species at the particular site. In Svalbard, the increase in tourism traffic is happening at a time when the endemic arctic species, in general, are showing a downward trend (Bengtsson et al., 2022; Descamps & Strøm, 2021). Several seabird species, as well as the polar bear and walrus, are on the Norwegian red list, which means that they are threatened by extinction (Artsdatabanken, 2021). Since hunting significantly reduced the polar bear population, a ban on hunting was introduced in 1973 (Aars et al., 2017). As a result, the population grew until the early 2000s, and while still on the red list, the population has been fairly stable since (Aars et al., 2017). Other hunted species, such as walrus, have shown similar developments (Kovacs et al., 2014). In contrast, most endemic Arctic seabirds, such as the ivory gull (*Pagophila eburna*) or Brünnich's guillemots (*Uria lomvia*), are declining, and their populations have been reducing by approximately 3%–5% per year (Descamps et al., 2013; Strøm et al., 2020). There is a concern, as reflected in the government's hearing statement for new environmental regulations in Svalbard, that the climate and environmental changes will make species more vulnerable to other types of stressors, including human activities (NEA, 2022).

Before the new amendments in Svalbard, there were several calls for more information about disturbance effects and vulnerability indicators and more knowledge-driven management in Svalbard (Hagen et al., 2012; Hovelsrud et al., 2023). In a comprehensive review of the existing literature on the effects of human activities on vegetation, fauna, and cultural heritage in Svalbard, Hagen et al. (2012) found that a certain level of scientific knowledge was available. This allowed the researchers to roughly grade the vulnerability of different landing sites, but they called for more site-specific data as a basis for more evidence-based management.

Methods

This study draws on both qualitative and quantitative methods. Quantitative methods have been used to assess expedition cruise tourism traffic, while a qualitative approach was preferred to solicit the perceived legitimacy of the proposed regulation.

AIS data collection and analysis

To discuss the rationale behind the new regulations, we assessed the development of the magnitude and distribution of expedition cruise ships and conventional cruise ships (hereafter 'cruise ships') during 2011–2022. The data used for operating the model (see Simonsen et al., 2018) were obtained from Norwegian Coastal Authorities (Kystverket), which comprise AIS registrations of most ship movements in a defined geographical area (Svalbard) with 5-min time intervals. AIS is an automatic tracking system for ships. Data were obtained for all years from 2011 to 2022.

Svalbard was defined as a geographical rectangle bounded by latitudes between 76.4° and 81° and longitudes between 10° and 33°. This yielded a dataset of 13,037,791 records delivered by Norwegian coastal authorities. They also delivered 118,458 records with east longitudes between 3° and 10° and consistent with the latitudes defined for Svalbard. We

included these records, resulting in a dataset of 13,156,249 records representing ships' sailing movements.

The AIS data also included the ships' speed, which was used to calculate the distance traveled during each 5-min interval, as well as the engine load and fuel consumption, based on the registered ships' installed power. This information was obtained from several websites and registered in a database developed by the Western Norway Research Institute (WNRI) during previous research projects.

Only passenger ships were included in the analysis, which were divided into two groups: cruise ships and expedition cruise ships. Expedition cruise ships are defined as ships with a maximum number of passengers below 500 and a minimum of 12. These definitions were applied by the WNRI based on detailed knowledge about each ship traveling in the Svalbard area between 2011 and 2022 and were cross-checked with the database. In total, there were 135 unique maritime mobile service identity (MMSI) numbers (i.e. the unique value identifying ships in the AIS system,) that had at least one registration over the years 2011–2022.

The unique MMSI numbers in the dataset are listed in Appendix 1, with their gross weight, year of built, and number of berths. If a ship changes flag and/or ownership during its lifetime, its MMSI number changes as well (www.itu.int). Therefore, some of the 135 ships are registered with different MMSI numbers, implying that we have 128 unique ships. These ships are listed by their MMSI numbers in Appendix 1, since this is the dataset used to retrieve the AIS data for the ships. Therefore, if somebody wants to repeat our analysis, they should use the MMSI numbers, not the ship names.

Qualitative methods

This study was based on qualitative methods, including an analysis of public responses to the 2022 regulatory hearing, and qualitative field research carried out between 2021 and 2024. The qualitative research design achieved an open and iterative research process, which allowed us to focus on identifying and understanding new discoveries and relationships under way (Maxwell, 2022). The rationale for such an approach was to facilitate collaborative and flexible research sensitive to the context and to encourage the co-production of knowledge with stakeholders (Hovelsrud & Westskog, 2023). This was to acknowledge calls for adaptive approaches to studying the multifaceted complexities and rapid changes facing the Arctic region (Ren et al., 2024).

The hearing of the new regulations was circulated in September 2021, with a final consultation deadline in May 2022. The NEA held a consultation meeting in Longyearbyen in November 2021. At the closing, the hearing received 110 responses from diverse groups of stakeholders, including local outdoor organizations, Norwegian universities and research institutes, and cruise operators and stakeholders from the tourism industry. We analyzed the hearing responses based on the aspects of the hearing that were questioned or criticized. We also carried out a document analysis of relevant gray literature, company strategies and webpages, as well as policy and regulatory documents.

We conducted several rounds of fieldwork and gathered information through exploratory interviews, semi-structured interviews, and workshops. During an initial scoping field trip in 2021, relevant stakeholders were identified through purposeful snowball sampling (Parker et al., 2020). These included tourism actors, such as business operators and guides; representatives from tourism organizations; and community members, elected officials, and civil servants representing administrative agencies overseeing

tourism and environmental management in Svalbard. On the following field trips, 24 in-depth interviews were conducted, each lasting between 30 and 90 min. Before being coded into thematic areas for analysis, the interviews were recorded and transcribed using Vivo software for qualitative data analysis (Bazeley & Jackson, 2019).

To encourage the co-production of knowledge and an iterative research process, three separate stakeholder workshops were organized in 2022, 2023, and 2024. The overarching goal of the workshops was to discuss future tourism development in Svalbard, identifying drivers of change and pathways for desired developments. During the first workshop hosted in Longyearbyen in 2022, 20 local stakeholders were introduced to and asked to discuss scenarios describing potential futures in Svalbard, who then discussed adaptive co-management options based on these. The 2023 workshop, also held in Longyearbyen, brought together 26 tourism actors and 7 researchers as facilitators. This workshop focused on how local tourism actors in Svalbard can create new opportunities as they respond to ongoing transformative changes in the archipelago. Finally, the 2024 workshop was held in conjunction with 'Svalbard Day' in Oslo in March 2024, an annual event that brings together actors across the private sector, public sector, and civil society. This workshop was a dialogue seminar during which 11 participants were introduced to the main findings of the research on the management of tourism and the environment in Svalbard, followed by a discussion of the possibilities for adaptive co-management approaches. Most respondents to the hearing and workshop participants were from the tourism industry.

The study was reviewed and approved by an appropriate national research ethics agency. The researchers obtained verbal informed consent from the research participants by asking them to participate in the study, reading a recruitment statement, and providing a written consent form containing all contact information for the project leaders and the research team.

Spatio-temporal distribution of expedition cruise vessels and conventional cruise vessels

We analyzed ship activities for three categories of ships, cruise ships and expedition cruise ships, in the period 2011–2022. There was a clear reduction in all ship activities during the years of the Covid pandemic from 2019 to 2021, measured by nautical miles traveled. The activity levels rebounded so quickly that the overall tourism traffic in 2022 was 87% higher than that in the last pre-pandemic year of 2018 (Figure 2), with 20% more unique ships accounted for. Thus, Svalbard tourism has more than recovered after the pandemic. In addition, the expedition cruise ships sailed longer cumulative distances in 2022 than ordinary cruise ships (Figure 2). This indicates a shift in Svalbard tourism after the pandemic years, with the activity geared toward smaller groups making longer trips on specially designed expedition ships. Such tourism costs more per passenger, since there are fewer passengers to share the costs. Svalbard tourism is, therefore, turning more toward an exclusive, luxurious activity for high-income clients.

Figure 3 shows the traffic in different geographical parts of Svalbard by ship type. Isfjorden is the fjord leading toward the major settlement and tourism hub of Longyearbyen and the Russian settlements of Barentsburg and Pyramiden. Nordvest-Spitsbergen is the north-western section of Svalbard, while Nordaustlandet is the northeastern part; these are the parts of Svalbard that are at the longest distance from the center at Longyearbyen. There is a shift with more travels, measured in nautical miles, to the north and less in Isfjorden

Figure 2. Barplot showing the annual sum of nautical miles (Nm) traveled around Svalbard per year per ship type. See [Figure 3](#) below for the bounding box used to geographically define the Svalbard region. The number above each bar indicates the unique count of ships of that type detected around Svalbard for the given year, as determined from the MMSI numbers in the AIS data.

around the main city of Longyearbyen and the Russian cities of Pyramiden and Barentsburg.

In 2019, 108,830 people went ashore on landing sites outside the main settlements, which represents a 60% increase from 2018. MOSJ explained this abrupt change through a significant increase in the number of expedition cruise ships, longer sailing seasons, and increased marketing of Svalbard as a travel destination (MOSJ, 2024). The number of expedition ship passengers going on shore in 2022 was 94,982, indicating that this part of the cruise industry is almost back to pre-COVID levels. As shown in [Figure 4](#), expedition cruise traffic now covers almost the entire coastline of the Svalbard archipelago.

Our dataset is from 2011–2022. Recent data from the Norwegian Coastal Administration (kystverket.no) show a significant increase again from 2022 to 2023, based on the number of port of calls in Longyearbyen, from 150 in 2019, 270 in 2022, to 360 in 2023.

The question then is what impact this increase in ship mileage and landings has on marine and coastal ecosystems. While there is limited knowledge and evidence of local impact, the literature review above indicates that disturbance effects are likely. See [Appendix 2](#) for detailed heatmaps of locations with both landing sites and nesting sites.

Analyzing legitimacy

Our results illustrate visually the increasing tourism traffic around Svalbard and [Figure 4](#) shows how the traffic corresponds with monitored nesting sites. With trends pointing toward future increase in traffic, and environmental aims of undisturbed areas, new environmental regulations are not surprising.

The interviews, fieldwork and analysis of hearing comments revealed that the tourism stakeholders opposed particularly the new limitations of expedition cruise landing sites (43 designated sites) and limitation on passenger numbers (200 passengers). While these

Figure 3. Map of the Svalbard bounding box used to extract ship AIS data. The years 2011, 2018, and 2022 are shown for their particular interest, respectively, as the first year of available data, the last pre-pandemic year, and the most recent year of available data. Note that each ship record represents approximately 5 min of ship time at a given location, and the values shown here are log₁₀ transformed (i.e. 1 = 10, 2 = 100, 3 = 1,000, etc.). The brighter a region of the map, the more consistent traffic that region sees.

changes were the essence of the protests, the discussion below outline the central components of the critique. In the following we will use the division between procedural (input) and performance (output) legitimacy to organize the material. Thus, we discuss (a) different aspects of the hearing process and how it was experienced by tourism stakeholders, (b) how the content of the regulations was experienced (with diverging views of how the precautionary principle should be used), and finally, (c) the expected efficiency of the regulations in terms of how successfully the regulations will be related to the major aim of preserving Svalbard's wilderness. Taken together this will increase our understanding of what preconditions need to be in place for environmental regulations based on the precautionary principle to be considered legitimate by stakeholders.

Procedural legitimacy: the process leading to the final environmental regulations

In September 2021, the Norwegian government began its public consultation process regarding the suggested amendments to SEPA regulations. In Norwegian public administration, a consultation process is used by the ministry to consult affected parties on suggested laws and regulations, suggested changes in public administration, jurisdiction changes, etc.

Figure 4. Heatmap of tourist traffic around Svalbard in 2022. Total tourist landings per site are shown as red dots of various sizes, while seabird nesting sites in Isfjorden and Kongsfjorden with current monitoring activities are shown as labeled blue squares.

The NAE, the government agency in charge of the process, hosted an open ‘consultation meeting’ in Longyearbyen in November 2021, where the proposed amendments were presented, and then the participants could express their views and ask questions. In addition, the stakeholders were invited to provide written comments, which they understood as one of the main venues for them to voice their concerns regarding the proposed regulatory amendments.

However, informants in Longyearbyen subsequently complained that even their most straightforward and uncontroversial suggestions were ignored in the final version of the hearing document. Even the factual errors and spelling mistakes that were pointed out in the first round were retained. This caused frustration and was seen as a breach of trust in governmental officials.

The experienced lack of involvement was reflected in several hearing comments, particularly from the tourism industry: ‘Lack of genuine involvement of affected parties; we perceive that this is not in accordance with good administrative practice’ (Hearing comment: Wild-photo Travel).

Being a major stakeholder that will be highly affected by the regulations, the Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (AECO) expected to be included in the amendment process and was not content with the level of involvement: ‘... *At the top of our list is the lack of engagement with the expedition cruise industry*’ (Hearing comment: Quark Expeditions). Members of AECO have been sailing in the area for years and developed their own site-specific guidelines for the operators to follow. One of the AECO members expressed frustration over not having any voice in the site selection process: ‘*Lack of dialogue with the industry when selecting the sites, considering that the industry players are the final users of the sites*’ (Hearing comment: Aurora).

Wallner (2008) highlight the importance of time in regulation processes. Given the quite comprehensive amendments, which would require careful consideration, several stakeholders felt that the process had been hasty: ‘*The process leading up to the consultation proposals has been weak and characterised by haste*’ (Hurtigruten expeditions). Others voiced, ‘*The prerequisite for a successful implementation is a successful preliminary process. In our view, this has not happened, but the time to turn around and start anew is not over*’ (Visit Svalbard).

While several respondents voiced such concern, the main critique of the hearing process came from expedition cruise industry actors. As major stakeholders, they expected to be involved more in the processes related to their activities.

Finding a balance between efficient regulations (in terms of reaching regulatory aims) and democratic processes is important and clearly recognized in our data. In mainland Norway, there has been a gradual move toward a more participatory approach to environmental management, with more power placed at the municipality level. While there are many good reasons for decentralizing power, Hovik (2008) warned that a more participatory approach may not favor the majority but rather the strong local stakeholders. More participation does not necessarily mean that everyone is heard equally.

Performance legitimacy: diverging perceptions of scientific documentation and the use of the precautionary principle

The output of the amendment process is the actual SEPA regulations and the documents that outline the background and justification for the changes. Comprehensive and complex environmental regulations will affect the user groups of Svalbard nature differently. This is illustrated by the range of statements and concerns from user groups that see their activity as being threatened by the regulations. The following citations from the hearing responses illustrate the concerns raised by the tourism industry and local inhabitants:

The regulations now proposed will have dramatic consequences for the economy of many tourism businesses. (Arctic Wildlife Tours)

To maintain a safe and stable Norwegian settlement, it is important that changes in environmental regulations do not hinder an active outdoor life. (Longyearbyen Hunting and Fisher Association)

The Svalbard nature is a central part of many people in Svalbard’s working life, as well as leisure time, and it is not surprising that the comprehensive regulatory changes meet criticism from different parts of the local society. What is interesting from the perspective of legitimacy is how the responses question the *justifications* of the amendments. First, the

scientific knowledge bases of the amendments are seen as insufficient, particularly by stakeholders from the tourism industry: *'Banning an activity without strong evidence against it is simply ignoring the facts and acting compulsively to the unknown'* (Aurora).

Another tourism stakeholder details this, referring to amendments opposing scientific advice:

There is a lack of empirical data, analysis, and knowledge behind the intrusive measures being proposed. Several measures also go against professional advice from, amongst others, the Norwegian Institute for Natural Research (NINA) and the Norwegian Polar Institute. The proposals are largely based on the precautionary principle, even where the necessary expertise exists or could have been obtained. (Hurtigruten expeditions)

The NEA refers to several scientific studies showing the negative impacts of human activities. However, as stated above, critics in the tourism industry claim that they ignored studies that showed limited or no disturbance, alleging that the government 'cherry picked' their sources. Such contestation over knowledge when there is high uncertainty and high stakes is common in many fields (Dannevig & Dale, 2018; Ney, 2009). This also shows that legitimacy cannot rest on 'unpartial' and 'objective' scientific knowledge alone, but that stakeholder participation in knowledge production and policy development is required (Dannevig & Dale, 2018).

As shown in the literature review above, there have, so far, been few and fragmented studies of disturbance effects on wildlife in Svalbard. In addition to scant disturbance studies from Svalbard, the hearing note (NEA, Chapter 5.3) refers to international research on disturbance effects, the vulnerability of arctic species due to the short time window for reproduction, and changes in access to food due to climate change. This, combined with the challenges of measuring disturbance effects at the population level discussed above, indicates that requests to build 'strong evidence' will be hard to meet. The demand for more knowledge is increasing in environmental governance, reinforced by uncertainties related to global climate change (Bay-Larsen, 2014).

Stakeholders, particularly those from the tourism industry, question the use of the precautionary principle. Informants in the tourism industry have been critical of the government's use of the precautionary principle (minutes from workshop #2), as they claim that the government is ignoring knowledge which shows that disturbance effects are negligible. This can also be seen in the following citation from a hearing comment: *'We are also critical of the proposed distance to walrus; existing research is being ignored in favour of the precautionary principle'* (Basecamp Explorer).

The stakeholders are well informed and criticize the use of the precautionary principle in a situation where research shows that disturbance can be tolerated by certain species.

UNESCO states that there needs to be some evidence to back up the employment of the precautionary principle (UNESCO/COMEST, 2005). However, it is a matter of expert judgment to decide what such evidence should be. The section above nuanced the complexities of measuring disturbance effects at the population level at a time when the living conditions are changing rapidly as an effect of climate change.

In a discussion of knowledge in Norwegian environmental planning, Bay-Larsen (2014, p. 275) described it as a tricky balancing act in natural resource management to 'be open about how knowledge is being packed and adjusted to political, economic and administrative frames and priorities without weakening the impact of the knowledge'. In this case, both the lack of openness and the scientific justification are questioned.

Related to this are disagreements on what *valid sources of knowledge* are. An example of this is the government's neglect of the site-specific guidelines developed by AECO. The hearing note has few references to the work of the cruise industry and, instead, suggests that this work should be disbanded. This is at odds with stakeholders who see site-specific knowledge as highly valuable:

Therefore, we believe that the more general regulations being proposed can certainly be implemented, but they should not replace site-specific guidelines. Site-specific guidelines of AECO's quality should, if possible, be implemented as common standards for all tourist activities at the permitted landing sites. (Birdlife Svalbard)

The classic schism between expert, scientific knowledge, and more experience-based knowledge is also highlighted in the hearing comments. The tourism actors operating in the field throughout the tourism season argue that they have a different knowledge base and understanding of the environment than the bureaucrats and that their experience-based knowledge should be included to a larger degree:

It is time for the authorities to sit down and listen to the expertise we have in the field after hundreds of days spent travelling in the Arctic and other natural environments. We are the ones who observe animal behaviour daily on our trips. (Arctic Wildlife Tours)

The performance legitimacy in terms of the regulatory documents is thus questioned, particularly by stakeholders from the tourism industry, who are critical to the scientific bases of the documents and the prominent use of the precautionary principle.

Performance legitimacy: the aim of preserving Arctic wilderness

Finally, performance legitimacy is also about the efficiency of regulations in terms of how they meet the stated aim of maintaining the Svalbard wilderness. A complete analysis of these aspects of performance legitimacy would require examination of future compliance with the amendments as well as their long-term effects. As the process has just been settled, this section will only investigate how the aims of the amendments correspond to our findings of increasing traffic and how the stakeholders view the correspondence between the environmental aims of Svalbard and the new amendments.

The aims of the environmental regulations in Svalbard are not only about preserving Arctic wildlife but also contain an experience dimension, as stated in *Svalbard*, the Government White Paper nr 22:53: *'The opportunities to experience Svalbard's nature undisturbed by motorized traffic and noise should be preserved, even in areas that are easily accessible from the settlements'*.

The quality of 'undisturbedness' is emphasized in the overall objectives in 12 of the 29 protected areas in Svalbard: 7 national parks and 5 nature reserves (Neumann, 2020, p. 314). These 12 large, protected areas cover nearly all protected areas in Svalbard, while the other 17 (mainly bird sanctuaries) together cover only a small fraction of the total protected terrestrial and marine areas.

Our results show major changes in marine traffic around the archipelago. The above heatmap shows a substantial increase in expedition cruise traffic between 2011 and 2022, in terms of both the number of ships and the distance traveled per ship. In addition, the cruise industry is expecting considerable growth in the years to come (Kystverket, 2024). Several popular landing spots are also close to the monitored bird nesting colonies

(Figure 4). This supports the government's justification for amendments to existing regulations.

All stakeholders agree on the importance of preserving the wilderness in Svalbard but disagree on how to achieve this. The citation below captures the essence of several of the tourism stakeholders. They are concerned with increasing traffic but highlight closer cooperation as opposed to stronger regulations:

We understand increased tourism is of concern. To that end, we need to strengthen our collaboration with the authorities in order to ensure sustainable tourism operations and development. (Polar Sails)

According to the tourism stakeholders, more collaboration and increased use of site-specific guidelines are important tools for handling the increase in traffic. A major challenge for nature conservation, in general, is weighing local, shorter-term interests against long-term conservation. In an analysis of the early effects of the Nature Diversity Act for mainland Norway (Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2009), Fauchald and Gulbrandsen (2012) questioned the long-term effects of decentralizing power in environmental decision-making, as they saw a 'considerable risk that user interests will prevail over long-term conservation interests'.

Bastmeijer and Roura (2004, p. 781) argued that, in the case of tourism in Antarctica, even though the industry's initiatives on self-regulation are valuable, they have limitations in terms of the commercial interests involved. They emphasized that management should first be guided by environmental aims.

While there are twofold management aims in Svalbard to both support the tourism industry and preserve the wilderness areas, the law clearly states that in case of conflict, the environment should always be given priority.

In terms of legitimacy, stakeholders from the tourism industry seem frustrated and concerned with what they see as a lack of will to cooperate. In the hearing response, one stakeholder expressed concern for the consequences of the new amendments:

I personally believe that, unfortunately, this will end up as a disdain towards the administration, and a weakening of the Norwegian support for and the management of the Svalbard treaty. (Hearing response, individual HV)

Based on the above findings we have summarized measures that will enhance legitimacy in environmental decision making based on the precautionary principle. That being said, the tension between industry and environmental policy makers will not necessarily be solved through such 'technical' measures, as conflicting aims and worldviews always will shape how the process and regulations are experienced. Legitimacy is context dependent and always dependent on who you ask (Lister, 2003).

Conclusion

Our review shows that the threat of disturbance from tourism activities is well-founded, considering the growth in number of expedition cruise ships and distance traveled by these ships, and with climate change as an important backdrop. Expedition cruise tourism is taking place close to important nesting sites for seabirds and in the habitats of other vulnerable species. Knowledge about the actual impacts on wildlife is still lacking, and not surprisingly the new amendments, which in part is

based on the precautionary principle (NEA, 2022), was met with fierce criticism from the tourism industry and local actors in Longyearbyen. The discussion above illustrates the challenges of basing environmental regulations on the precautionary principle.

What preconditions and measures should be in place in order to increase the perceived legitimacy among affected stakeholders? Stakeholder involvement and participation are increasingly being viewed as key to legitimacy and compliance in environmental governance (Birnbaum, 2016). In our case, from the perspective of procedural legitimacy, the lack of true and meaningful inclusion and participation were highlighted by the stakeholders. While the public participation procedures were followed by the authorities, the stakeholders experienced a hasty process where their voices were not listened to. A more inclusive process and dialogue would have strengthened the procedural legitimacy of the amendments (see also Table 2).

An example of how the initiatives of the expedition cruise industry has been neglected, is that their site-specific guidelines now are being repealed (NEA, 2022). This is criticized both by actors from the tourism industry and other stakeholders concerned with more particular monitoring of species (Hagen et al., 2012; Hovelsrud et al., 2023). While the industry-initiated guidelines are seen as a valuable management approach by the stakeholders, the use of site-specific guidelines has also been criticized, as the abstention of the authorities to use its regulatory power can cause an evolution of different and diverging standards, gaps in implementation and compliance, and other issues of inconsistency (Neumann, 2020, p. 326).

In terms of performance legitimacy, the justifications for using the precautionary principle were not experienced as convincing by the stakeholders. First, more time and resources could have been used to communicate the magnitude and cascading effects of climate change. While the growth in expedition cruise tourism is considerable, this comes on top of unprecedented environmental changes where the effects on species and eco systems are still mostly unknown. The severity of this situation could have been given more attention in the justification for the amendments. While our findings are linked to the Svalbard case, the importance of justifying and communicating well why the precautionary principle is employed cannot be underestimated.

Secondly, while the current, and growing, magnitude and distribution of expedition cruise vessels and associated activities can have adverse effects on wildlife (Llobet et al., 2023; Øian & Kaltenborn, 2020), this is for now poorly documented. As the stakeholders point out, there are severe knowledge gaps in terms of the threshold levels and indicators that can be used to define carrying capacity of the ecosystems to expedition cruise

Table 2. Proposals for enhancing legitimacy and reducing conflicts.

Measure	Questions for policy makers
Better communication	Is the core of the uncertainty (the reason for employing the precautionary principle) communicated well enough, both in public meetings and in written form? In this case: the combined effects of climate change and increased visitation
More participation	Have stakeholders been included in the regulatory process? Have the participation and input from stakeholders had any impact on the regulatory process or amendments to regulations?
More transparency	Is the regulatory process experienced as transparent, including how input from stakeholders is being incorporated?
Improved scientific basis	Has there been sufficient time and public meetings during the regulatory process to discuss the scientific basis with stakeholders? Have more adaptive approaches been tested (in this case e.g. co-development of indicators and thresholds for expedition cruise ships)? If not, is the reason for leaving out such approaches clearly communicated?
Better inclusion	Are perspectives and input from stakeholders included in the process and is it transparent why or why not these are part of the final regulations?

tourism. In addition, the implementation of such devices necessitates monitoring programs and relevant time series data, neither of which exist in Svalbard. The contestation of the application of the precautionary principle must be understood in this context. The stakeholders asked for less use of the precautionary principle and more impact assessments and monitoring. This has also been recognized by research (Hagen et al., 2012; Hovelsrud et al., 2023).

In an older study from Svalbard, Vistad et al. (2008, p. 103) argued that limiting traffic based on the precautionary principle ‘may seem convenient, arrogant and provoking, and destroy the interaction between actors needing mutual trust and cooperation’. The citations from the stakeholders above support their predictions, and it is still an open question whether the lack of ‘evidence’ for disturbance will impact compliance with the new regulation amendments due to its contested legitimacy.

In Antarctica, similar challenges of increasing seaborne tourism have, so far, been met with less strict measures, and there researchers are calling for increased use of the precautionary principle, not as a way of banning the industry but as a ‘practical instrument to the management of tourism, which may result in imposing certain restrictions on tourist activities’ (Bastmeijer & Roura, 2004, p. 772).

Based on previous research, there is still no reason to believe that more knowledge alone will reduce conflict (Dannevig & Dale, 2018; Ney, 2009). When both uncertainties and stakes are high, participation and value diversity are also needed in the production of knowledge for policy (e.g. Funtowicz & Ravetz, 1994; Nogueira et al., 2021). While there will always be tension between the needs of industry and those of environmental protection, an adaptive co-management approach to the development of indicators and thresholds for expedition cruise tourism management might reduce the level of conflict, ensure the protection of vulnerable Arctic ecosystems, and provide greater flexibility than that provided by the proposed amendments.

While mainland Norway has moved toward more multidimensional management, the recent regulation process has shown that environmental management in Svalbard remains on a more conservative track. This is in line with the stated environmental aims but could also be seen in relation to other recent legal adjustments in Svalbard, which point toward tightened state control (Sokolickova et al., 2022).

Our analysis shows that regulations based on the precautionary principle need to pay extra attention to processes of participation, transparency and inclusion, and in Table 2 in the previous section we propose how such processes can be addressed. The reason for applying the precautionary principle must also be clearly communicated. The new amendments to regulations in Svalbard lack legitimacy among local stakeholders due to deficiencies in both the process and disagreements about the scientific basis of the hearing. Looking at the significant growth in cruise tourism in combination with Svalbard’s environmental aims, it is not surprising that strong environmental measures are effectuated. What is surprising is the lack of true dialogue in the process.

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